

Report

The evaluation of existing training courses
about depopulation and killing of rabbits on
farm

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1 Executive Summary

In this document, the Centre for Animal Welfare for Poultry and other Small Farmed Animals (EURCAW-Poultry-SFA) reviews and assess the existing training courses and materials about depopulation and/or killing of rabbits on farm in use at Member States (MS). The Centre received only two presentations from one MS, and a factsheet from the EU Commission about how to stun/kill rabbits on farm as a reference from another MS. Training material on this topic is scarce.

EURCAW-Poultry-SFA will publish a review about currently available methods for on-farm killing of growing rabbits, breeding rabbits and kits, and a survey on currently used methods for on-farm killing that will target EU rabbit-producing MS.

EURCAW-Poultry-SFA will organise during 2027 a webinar about this topic, based on the results presented in the review.

2 Introduction

EURCAW-Poultry-SFA reviewed and assessed the existing training courses and materials about depopulation and/or killing of rabbits on farm in use at MS or at other levels (e.g., regional training courses).

Thus, EURCAW-Poultry-SFA requested the National training materials to all the EU MS. The report includes a description of the existing courses and materials as well as an identification of the gaps that the Centre might address in the future.

3 Methodology

The EURCAW-Poultry-SFA requested from the Competent Authority contact points at the beginning of 2025 the National training materials (from 2010 to 2024) about depopulation and/or killing of rabbits on farm. The Centre received feedback from eight MS. However, only one of them provided national training materials about this topic:

- One presentation about how to inspect rabbits' farms. It includes a slide about authorised methods for killing on farm.
- One presentation about welfare on rabbits' farms. It includes a slide about humane end points with the EU Commission Factsheet about how to stun/kill rabbits on farm, but no further development.

Another MS also shared the EU Commission Factsheet about how to stun/kill rabbits on farm. This factsheet is a good support document, but a training course should include a wider description of the concepts.

4 Gaps of knowledge

In order to ensure the most humane and effective killing of rabbits during depopulation or on farm killing of individuals, specific training is needed. The main producers Member States of rabbits in the European Union are Spain, Italy, and France (Eurostat, 2022¹). However, the only training material we received is not from them, and the materials provided have scarce information.

With the concern about this topic in mind, EURCAW-Poultry-SFA is currently working to perform a review about currently available methods for on-farm killing of growing rabbits, breeding rabbits and kits, and a survey on currently used methods for on-farm killing that will target EU

¹ Consultation of the Eurostat database "Main livestock indicators by NUTS 2 regions" (data coverage: 2013-2020), for "Live rabbits and breeding females", online data code: EF_LSK_MAIN, last update: 03/10/2022 23:00.

rabbit-producing MS. This review will detail the on-farm killing methods for rabbits approved under Regulation (EC) No 1099/2009, which dictates the protection of animals at the time of killing. The review will assess the advantages and disadvantages of these methods in terms of animal welfare, as well as identify existing gaps of knowledge. In addition, a survey will be conducted to investigate on-farm culling practices used in EU rabbit-producing countries by sending an online questionnaire to the competent authorities concerned. The findings from this survey will be integrated into the review to provide a broader perspective on current practices.

Furthermore, EURCAW-Poultry-SFA plans to organise during 2027 a webinar about this topic, based on the results presented in the review.

5 Conclusions

1. One Member State have training materials about depopulation and/or killing of rabbits on farm, to EURCAW-Poultry-SFA knowledge.
2. Information provided in these materials is really scarce.
3. The EU Commission Factsheet about how to stun/kill rabbits on farm is a good support document, but a training course should include a wider description of the concepts.

6 Further actions

1. EURCAW-Poultry-SFA plans to perform a review about currently available methods for on-farm killing of growing rabbits, breeding rabbits and kits, and a survey on currently used methods for on-farm killing that will target EU rabbit-producing MS.
2. EURCAW-Poultry-SFA plans to offer during 2027 a webinar about this topic, based on the results presented in the review.

About EURCAW-Poultry-SFA

EURCAW-Poultry-SFA is one of the four European Union Reference Centres for Animal Welfare. It focuses on poultry and other small farmed animals welfare and legislation, and covers the entire life cycle from hatch/birth to the end of life. EURCAW-Poultry-SFA's main objective is to scientifically and technically support the European Commission and Member States for implementation of welfare legislation. This includes:

- Directive 98/58/EC concerning the protection of animals kept on farms;
- Regulations 1/2005/EC and 1099/2009/EC concerning their protection during transport and slaughter;
- Directive 1999/74/EC laying down minimum standards for the protection of laying hens;
- Directive 2007/43/EC laying down minimum rules for the protection of chickens kept for meat production.

Partners

EURCAW-Poultry-SFA receives funding from DG SANTE of the European Commission and represents a collaboration between the following four partner institutions:

- ANSES, France
- IRTA, Spain
- ANIVET, AU, Denmark
- IZSLER, Italy

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Activities of EURCAW-Poultry-SFA

- Coordinated Assistance
Providing support, networking and Questions to EURCAW;
- Welfare indicators, Assessment & Good Practices
Identifying animal welfare indicators, including animal based, management based and resource-based indicators, that can be used to verify compliance with the EU legislation;
- Scientific and technical studies
Preparing Scientific Reviews of knowledge on welfare topics, identify research needs and perform scientific and technical studies to fill the gaps of knowledge;
- Training
Reviewing existing training activities and developing new training materials, webinars and knowledge pills for official inspectors and competent authorities;
- Communication and Dissemination
Increasing awareness of our outputs via the website, and newsletter.

Website and contact

EURCAW-Poultry-SFA's website offers relevant and actual information to support enforcement of poultry and other small farmed animals' welfare legislation.

We offer a 'Questions to EURCAW' service for official inspectors, policy workers, and other personnel providing advice or support for official controls of poultry and other small farmed animals welfare in the EU. For more information go to the Q2E webform available online [here](#) or <https://survey.anses.fr/SurveyServer/s/DSL/Queryw>. All Q2E answers are available [online](#)

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